

Beyond the binary: Femme fatale, motherhood, and the instability of femininity in Dragon Age

İkili karşıtlıkların ötesinde: Dragon Age'de femme fatale, annelik ve istikrarsız kadınlık

AYLIN BERNA ZAMANDAR BAŞOĞLU

Arş. Gör., Beykoz Üniversitesi, Sanat ve Tasarım Fakültesi, Çizgi Film ve Animasyon Bölümü, ORCID: 0000-0002-4846-8273, bernabasoglu@beykoz.edu.tr

Geliş | Received: 03/05/2026 Kabul | Accepted: 23/06/2026 Yayım | Published: 25/06/2026 Benzerlik oranı | Similarity Ratio: 8% (Turnitin) Katkı oranı | Contribution ratio: Yazar 1: 100%

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the relationship between the femme fatale archetype and the concept of motherhood in digital games, focusing on how femininity is constructed and destabilized within interactive narrative systems. Drawing on feminist theory, particularly Julia Kristeva's concept of abjection, Barbara Creed's notion of the monstrous-feminine, and Judith Butler's theory of gender performativity, the study explores how maternal figures can simultaneously embody nurturing, threatening, and ambiguous qualities. The Dragon Age series (BioWare, 2009–2014) is analyzed as a case study through a qualitative textual analysis of the characters Flemeth and Morrigan. Rather than treating these figures as fixed representations, the analysis conceptualizes them as dynamic configurations shaped by narrative design, player agency, and interpretive engagement. In this context, femininity emerges not as a stable identity but as a performative and unstable process. The findings suggest that digital games do not simply reproduce gender stereotypes but actively reconfigure them through interactive systems. While elements of patriarchal ideology persist, characters such as Flemeth and Morrigan disrupt binary oppositions between motherhood and fatal femininity, revealing the limits of traditional representational frameworks. In this sense, digital games function as dynamic cultural spaces where gender is not only represented but continuously produced and renegotiated through play.

Keywords: femme fatale, motherhood, femininity, digital games, Dragon Age

ÖZ

Bu çalışma, dijital oyunlarda femme fatale arketipi ile annelik kavramı arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemekte ve kadınlığın etkileşimli anlatı sistemleri içerisinde nasıl kurulduğunu ve istikrarsızlaştırıldığını ele almaktadır. Çalışma, feminist kuramdan yararlanarak özellikle Julia Kristeva'nın iğrençlik (abjection) kavramı, Barbara Creed'in canavar dişil (monstrous-feminine) yaklaşımı ve Judith Butler'in toplumsal cinsiyetin performatifliği kuramı çerçevesinde, annelik figürlerinin aynı anda hem besleyici hem tehditkâr hem de muğlak nitelikler taşıyabildiğini tartışmaktadır. Bu bağlamda, BioWare tarafından geliştirilen Dragon Age serisi (2009–2014) bir vaka çalışması olarak ele alınmış ve Flemeth ile Morrigan karakterleri nitel metin analizi yöntemiyle incelenmiştir. Bu figürler sabit temsiller olarak değil, anlatı tasarımı, oyuncu failliği ve etkileşim tarafından şekillenen dinamik yapılar olarak değerlendirilmiştir. Bu çerçevede kadınlık, sabit bir kimlikten ziyade performatif ve istikrarsız bir süreç olarak ortaya çıkmaktadır. Elde edilen bulgular, dijital oyunların toplumsal cinsiyet kalıplarını yalnızca yeniden üretmekle kalmayıp, etkileşimli sistemler aracılığıyla bu kalıpları yeniden yapılandırıldığını göstermektedir. Ataerkil ideolojinin izleri varlığını sürdürse de, Flemeth ve Morrigan gibi karakterler annelik ile femme fatale arasındaki ikili karşıtlıkları aşarak geleneksel temsil çerçevelerinin sınırlarını görünür kılmaktadır. Bu anlamda dijital oyunlar, toplumsal cinsiyetin yalnızca temsil edilmediği, aynı zamanda oyun deneyimi aracılığıyla sürekli olarak üretildiği ve yeniden müzakere edildiği dinamik kültürel alanlar olarak değerlendirilebilir.

Anahtar kelimeler: femme fatale, annelik, kadınlık, dijital oyunlar, Dragon Age

ATIF | CITATION

Zamandar Başoğlu, A. B. (2026). Beyond the binary: Femme fatale, motherhood, and the instability of femininity in Dragon Age. *Comm.design: Journal of Communication Design Research*, 1(1): 35–49. https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20846842

Introduction

The figure of the *femme fatale* has long occupied a paradoxical position within cultural narratives, functioning simultaneously as an object of desire and a source of danger. Tracing its roots to mythological and religious figures such as Lilith, Salome, and Cleopatra, this archetype has been repeatedly reconfigured across different media forms, particularly in cinema and popular culture. Yet, as feminist film theory has demonstrated, these representations have largely been shaped within a regime of visibility structured by patriarchal power. Laura Mulvey's concept of the "male gaze" remains central to understanding how female characters are framed as objects of visual pleasure, both within narrative worlds and for spectators themselves (Mulvey, 1975).

Digital games, despite their interactive nature, have historically reproduced similar representational patterns. Numerous studies have shown that female characters are frequently underrepresented, sexualized, or relegated to secondary narrative positions (Downs & Smith, 2010; Shaw, 2014). Even when women occupy central roles, their characterization often follows familiar conventions such as the "damsel in distress," the hypersexualized warrior, or the emotionally dependent companion. Open-world titles such as *Grand Theft Auto V* exemplify these dynamics through the marginalization and objectification of female figures, while many action-oriented narratives continue to rely on the trope of a male protagonist tasked with protecting, rescuing, or guiding a vulnerable female character. Yet the persistence of these conventions raises an important question: have representations of women fundamentally changed, or have existing archetypes simply been reconfigured in new forms?

Recent developments suggest a more complex picture. Games such as *The Last of Us Part II* (Naughty Dog, 2020), *Horizon Zero Dawn* (Guerrilla Games, 2017), and *Control* (Remedy Entertainment, 2019) have introduced female protagonists whose identities extend beyond conventional gendered roles. These shifts have coincided with broader debates surrounding diversity and representation within the game industry, where female players now constitute a substantial proportion of the global gaming audience. Nevertheless, many contemporary representations continue to rely on recognizable archetypal frameworks. Female characters are often legitimized through traits traditionally associated with masculinity, such as physical strength, emotional restraint, or individualistic heroism, while alternative forms of feminine power receive comparatively less attention. This tendency becomes particularly visible in discussions of motherhood. Existing research has generated important insights into the representation of women in digital games, yet motherhood is frequently examined through themes of care, sacrifice, protection, and emotional attachment. Comparatively less attention has been given to figures who simultaneously embody motherhood, sexuality, power, and threat. The possibility of the maternal figure as excessive, manipulative, transformative, or even monstrous often remains at the margins of game studies discussions. Julia Kristeva's concept of abjection offers a useful framework for approaching this absence, as it describes that which disrupts boundaries, provokes discomfort, and challenges the coherence of the subject (Kristeva, 1982). Building on this framework, Barbara Creed's notion of the *monstrous-feminine* demonstrates how maternal bodies in visual culture are frequently represented as sites of fear, transgression, and instability (Creed, 1993). Yet such configurations remain relatively uncommon in digital games, where motherhood is more often associated with nurturing, sacrifice, or narrative motivation than with power, ambiguity, and transformation.

Within this context, the *Dragon Age* series offers a particularly productive case. Developed by BioWare and first released in 2009, the series places questions of lineage, inheritance, transformation, and maternal power at the center of its narrative mythology. Across multiple installments, female characters do not merely occupy supporting roles but actively shape political, historical, and ontological structures within the game world. Among these figures, Flemeth and Morrigan are especially significant because they simultaneously embody aspects of maternal identity and fatal femininity while resisting straightforward moral categorization. While *Dragon Age* has frequently been discussed within game studies for its inclusion of queer romance options (Ruberg, 2019), considerably less attention has been paid to the ways in which the series reconfigures femininity through the intersection of motherhood, monstrosity, and power.

This study examines these questions through a qualitative textual analysis of Flemeth and Morrigan across the Dragon Age series. Rather than positioning women solely as objects of desire or agents of care, these characters occupy a liminal space that complicates binary understandings of femininity, power, and morality. By focusing on the relationship between motherhood, monstrosity, and female agency, the study explores how digital game narratives can provide alternative ways of imagining femininity beyond conventional oppositions such as nurturing/destructive, passive/active, or victim/threat.

In doing so, the article suggests that digital games should not be understood merely as spaces that reproduce existing gender norms, but also as narrative environments in which these norms are negotiated, contested, and reimagined through both storytelling and player interpretation.

Theoretical background and representation of women in digital games

Discussions of gender in digital games have traditionally been framed through questions of representation, particularly focusing on the absence, marginalization, and sexualization of female characters. This tendency is further reinforced by the construction of idealized and often unattainable body standards, where female characters are designed according to exaggerated physical proportions that prioritize visual appeal over realism (Martins et al., 2009). Early studies demonstrated that women were either excluded from game worlds or positioned as secondary figures with limited narrative agency. However, more recent scholarships suggest that representation alone cannot fully explain the complexity of how femininity is constructed within games.

A significant development in this literature is the shift toward broader socio-cultural and psychological frameworks. As Tompkins et al. argue, video game characters are not neutral constructs but "reflect collective choices of game developers shaped, in part, by their socio-cultural contexts" (2020, p. 237). This perspective moves beyond identifying problematic portrayals and instead asks why certain representations persist. In doing so, it situates character design within a network of cultural values, norms, and expectations.

One of the most productive frameworks for analyzing these dynamics is ambivalent sexism theory. Rather than treating sexism as a singular phenomenon, Glick and Fiske (2001) conceptualize it as consisting of two interrelated forms: hostile sexism and benevolent sexism. Hostile sexism frames women as manipulative, dangerous, or threatening, particularly when they display power or autonomy. The figure of the *femme fatale* exemplifies this logic, emerging historically as a response to anxieties surrounding women's increasing social power. In contrast, benevolent sexism idealizes women as pure, innocent, and in need of protection, thereby reinforcing dependency while appearing positive. As Tompkins et al. note, this dual structure "fosters the perpetual subordination of women" by regulating their roles through complementary expectations (2020, p. 238).

This ambivalence is particularly visible in digital games, where female characters are often constructed as both empowered and constrained. As Tompkins et al. describe, female bodies frequently function simultaneously as "objects" and "weapons" (2020, p. 242), becoming sites of both visual consumption and narrative action.

This tension becomes especially visible in action-oriented female protagonists. The case of Lara Croft illustrates the paradox that has shaped much of the academic debate on gender and games. As one of the most recognizable female characters in digital game history, Croft is simultaneously powerful and sexualized, autonomous and objectified. Kennedy (2002) captures this contradiction by asking whether Lara Croft should be understood as a "feminist icon" or a "cyber-bimbo." This tension illustrates how empowerment and objectification often coexist rather than exclude one another in digital game representations of women.

This instability can also be understood through Butler's (1990) concept of gender performativity. Rather than treating femininity as a stable essence, Butler argues that gender is continuously produced through repeated performances and social expectations. From this perspective, the contradictory

representations identified in digital games do not simply reflect different types of women; they reveal the processes through which femininity itself is constructed, maintained, and contested. Recent game studies scholarship has similarly questioned fixed understandings of identity and representation. Rather than treating categories such as gender and sexuality as stable, Bonnie Ruberg (2019) argues that queerness names a way of imagining and inhabiting alternative possibilities beyond dominant norms and structures of power. From this perspective, the significance of game characters lies not only in whether they represent particular identities, but also in how they disrupt established categories and open space for alternative configurations of subjectivity. This perspective is particularly relevant for figures such as Flemeth and Morrigan, whose meanings emerge through ambiguity, transformation, and instability rather than through fixed definitions.

These debates also intersect with feminist media theory and game studies. Mulvey's (1975) concept of the male gaze explains how women are positioned as objects of visual pleasure, while game studies scholars have argued that interactivity complicates this dynamic. Shaw (2014), for example, suggests that representation does not automatically produce identification, while Consalvo (2008) emphasizes the role of production cultures and player communities in shaping gendered meanings. Moreover, Sicart (2013) argues that players engage with game systems ethically, interpreting characters not only as narrative figures but also as moral agents within interactive structures. Together, these perspectives indicate that representation in games operates not only through images but also through systems of interaction, interpretation, and cultural negotiation.

Contemporary games appear to offer more diverse representations. Titles such as *The Last of Us Part II* and *Horizon Zero Dawn* present complex female protagonists who occupy central narrative roles. However, this apparent shift does not fully resolve the contradictions identified in earlier scholarship. Characters may be narratively central and structurally powerful, yet their power often remains legible within existing cultural norms of agency, resilience, and control. At the same time, certain forms of femininity remain comparatively underexplored. While the literature has extensively examined sexualization, empowerment, and representation, less attention has been paid to figures associated with excess, transformation, ambiguity, and instability—concepts central to Kristeva's notion of abjection and Creed's theory of the *monstrous-feminine*.

Thus, the issue is not simply how women are represented, but which forms of femininity become narratively possible. The framework of ambivalent sexism helps explain how femininity is structured through opposing yet complementary forces, but it does not fully account for figures that exceed both idealization and threat. It is within this context that *Dragon Age* becomes analytically significant. Through characters such as Flemeth and Morrigan, the series provides a useful case for examining how motherhood, danger, seduction, and power intersect within contemporary representations of femininity.

Femme fatale, motherhood, and the limits of femininity

"Eroticism is mystique... There is a daemonic instability in sexual relations that we may have to accept."

— Camille Paglia, *Sexual Personae* (1990)

The figure of the femme fatale has long functioned as a privileged site for thinking about the instability of femininity across cultural forms. Rather than a purely modern invention, the archetype recurs from myth to modern media as a figure through which femininity becomes legible as excess—at once alluring and threatening. Classical accounts often interpret this figure as a projection of male anxiety; yet such a reading risks reducing the femme fatale to a derivative effect of patriarchy. A more productive approach situates her within a broader cultural struggle to regulate what appears as uncontrollable within femininity itself.

In this regard, Paglia's account of Western culture as structured by the tension between Apollonian order and Dionysian force provides a crucial entry point. In *Sexual Personae* (1990), femininity is repeatedly associated with nature, materiality, and an irreducible excess that resists rational classification. The

femme fatale, read through this lens, is not only a cultural stereotype but a symptom of this excess: a figure that marks the limits of symbolic order. Her threat does not lie simply in seduction or deception, but in her refusal to be stabilized within the categories that seek to define her. This instability is amplified when considered alongside Mary Ann Doane's (1991) argument that the femme fatale is fundamentally unreadable. She is not a coherent subject but a shifting signifier, whose meaning is constantly deferred. It is precisely this opacity that produces anxiety: the impossibility of fully knowing or containing the feminine. In this sense, the femme fatale is less a character type than a structural disturbance within representation itself. Butler's (1990) concept of gender performativity further complicates this figure by suggesting that femininity is not an essence but an effect of repeated acts and social expectations. From this perspective, the femme fatale appears not as a stable type but as a performative configuration whose meanings remain contingent and unstable.

Historically, this figure has been constructed in opposition to motherhood. Within dominant narratives, motherhood is aligned with care, stability, and moral order, while the femme fatale embodies autonomy, sexuality, and danger. The maternal body is idealized as contained and socially productive; the fatal woman is marked as excessive and disruptive. This binary, however, depends on a fragile conceptual boundary that does not withstand closer scrutiny. Feminist scholarship has long demonstrated that such oppositional constructions reduce femininity to limited and normative roles. As Inceoğlu (2015) argues, women in mainstream narratives are frequently positioned within oppositional categories such as the femme fatale and the innocent girl. However, feminist narratives disrupt not only these binaries but also the tendency to frame women solely as victims. From this perspective, the representation of femininity requires moving beyond fixed categories toward more fluid and complex configurations.

Maternal identity itself is not a neutral or purely nurturing category but one shaped by ideological regulation. It is culturally produced through norms that define acceptable femininity—norms that privilege self-sacrifice, purity, and containment. As such, motherhood functions not only as a role but as a disciplinary mechanism. It delineates the limits of permissible female behavior, rendering deviations—sexual autonomy, refusal, ambivalence—suspect or pathological. At the same time, historical accounts of the body reveal how these norms are embedded within broader cultural transformations. As Mikhail Bakhtin's analysis of the "classical body" suggests, the Renaissance and Enlightenment mark a shift toward representing the body as closed, complete, and self-contained, in contrast to earlier, more "grotesque" conceptions of the body as open, unfinished, and in flux. Processes such as growth, reproduction, and bodily transformation—central to the maternal body—are increasingly suppressed or excluded from representation. This shift reflects not only an aesthetic preference but a cultural project: the containment of what appears excessive, permeable, and uncontrollable. These tensions become particularly visible in contemporary fantasy narratives, where motherhood is frequently associated not only with care and continuity but also with transformation, excess, and bodily instability. The Dragon Age universe repeatedly frames maternity through images of violation, corporeal transformation, and monstrous reproduction. One of the most explicit examples appears in *Dragon Age: Origins*, where the creation of the Broodmother is recounted through a poem narrated by the dwarf Hespith. Describing the transformation of captive women into reproductive monsters, the poem states:

"Eighth day, we hated as she is violated. Ninth day, she grins and devours her kin. Now she does feast, as she's become the beast." (BioWare, 2009).

Notably, motherhood here is not represented as a natural or nurturing condition, but as the outcome of violation, bodily corruption, and forced reproduction. The maternal body becomes simultaneously reproductive and monstrous, functioning as a site where the boundaries between self and other, human and non-human, begin to collapse. Such representations resonate strongly with Kristeva's (1982) notion of abjection and Creed's (1993) formulation of the monstrous-feminine, both of which identify the maternal body as a privileged site of cultural anxiety.

Mythological narratives further reinforce this logic. The story of Apollo and Daphne, for example, stages the disciplining of female sexuality through transformation. Daphne's refusal of desire culminates not in

autonomy but in her conversion into a tree—an act that preserves her chastity by removing her from the realm of human relationality (Gürses Akbaykal, 2013, pp. 188–189). The narrative thus resolves the threat of female sexuality by translating it into a static, non-agentive form. Similarly, religious iconography—most notably the figure of the Virgin Mary—constructs motherhood through purity, detachment from sexuality, and bodily containment. The maternal figure is elevated precisely insofar as she is removed from the dynamics of desire and reproduction that define lived embodiment.

Yet these forms of containment are never complete. As Julia Kristeva argues, the maternal body occupies a fundamentally ambiguous position. In *Powers of Horror*, she defines abjection as a condition that “does not radically cut off the subject from what threatens it,” but instead maintains a disturbing proximity between self and other (Kristeva, 1982, p. 9). The maternal body is exemplary in this regard: it is both origin and alterity, both intimate and destabilizing. It cannot be fully assimilated into symbolic order because it continually exposes the fragility of boundaries.

Barbara Creed’s notion of the “monstrous-feminine” extends this argument by showing how maternal power is often represented as threatening precisely because of this ambiguity. In horror and visual culture, the maternal body appears not as purely nurturing but as excessive, transformative, and potentially destructive. Importantly, this threat does not originate outside the symbolic order but from within it. The maternal figure becomes monstrous not because she deviates from femininity, but because she reveals its unstable foundations.

From this perspective, the opposition between the *femme fatale* and the mother begins to collapse. Both figures are structured through attempts to regulate feminine excess, and both expose the limits of that regulation. While one is marked as dangerous and the other as idealized, both remain tied to forms of instability that resist containment. What differs is not their ontological status but the discursive frameworks through which they are rendered legible. This convergence invites a reconsideration of femininity itself. If both the *femme fatale* and the maternal figure are sites of excess, ambiguity, and boundary disruption, then their apparent opposition may be less a natural distinction than a cultural strategy of differentiation. The separation of these figures allows for the stabilization of femininity into manageable categories; their convergence, by contrast, reveals the inadequacy of those categories. This raises a central question for the present study: What forms of femininity become possible when the distinction between seduction and reproduction, danger and care, is no longer maintained?

It is precisely this question that remains insufficiently addressed in the context of digital games. While female characters are frequently categorized within recognizable archetypes—heroine, caregiver, seductress—the intersection of these roles is rarely sustained. Figures that combine maternal authority with fatal ambiguity tend to be marginalized, simplified, or contained within existing narrative frameworks.

This study approaches *Dragon Age* as a site in which this limitation is actively negotiated. Through characters such as Flemeth and Morrigan, the series does not merely reproduce familiar tropes but brings together elements that are typically kept apart. In doing so, it opens a space for rethinking femininity not as a stable category, but as a dynamic configuration of excess, ambiguity, and power. In this sense, the series offers a useful case for examining forms of femininity that exceed stable categories and resist fixed definitions (Ruberg, 2019).

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative textual analysis to examine the representation of femininity and motherhood in the *Dragon Age* series. Rather than treating digital games as static narrative texts, the study approaches them as interactive narrative systems in which meaning emerges through the interaction of narrative design, player agency, visual representation, and world-building structures (Bogost, 2007). Within this framework, femininity is understood not as a fixed characteristic of individual characters but as a dynamic construct produced through narrative events, character relationships, player interpretation, and cultural discourse.

The study focuses on Flemeth and Morrigan, two central female characters whose narrative trajectories extend across multiple installments of the *Dragon Age* franchise. These characters were selected through purposive case selection because they occupy a unique position at the intersection of motherhood, sexuality, femininity, power, and monstrosity. Both figures play a significant role in shaping the mythology, genealogical continuity, and broader narrative structure of the *Dragon Age* universe.

The primary corpus consists of narrative sequences, character interactions, codex materials, and visual representations drawn from *Dragon Age: Origins* (2009), *Dragon Age II* (2011), and *Dragon Age: Inquisition* (2014), together with selected expansion and downloadable content relevant to the narratives of Flemeth and Morrigan, particularly *Awakening* and *Witch Hunt* (2010). While the analysis primarily focuses on the mainline games, expansion content is included when it provides important narrative information concerning motherhood, lineage, character development, and the broader mythology of the *Dragon Age* universe. Particular attention was given to scenes in which motherhood, bodily transformation, inheritance, and female agency become central narrative concerns. These include Flemeth's introduction in the Korcari Wilds, the "Flemeth's Real Grimoire" quest, Flemeth's transformation into a High Dragon, Morrigan's proposal of the Dark Ritual, the narrative arc surrounding Kieran, and Morrigan's encounter with Mythal in *Dragon Age: Inquisition*. These scenes were selected because they represent key moments through which maternal identity, power transmission, and feminine ambiguity are articulated and negotiated. Together, these scenes constitute the primary analytical units of the study.

The analysis is informed by feminist film theory and psychoanalytic approaches, particularly Laura Mulvey's (1975) concept of the male gaze, Julia Kristeva's (1982) theory of abjection, Barbara Creed's (1993) notion of the monstrous-feminine, and Judith Butler's (1990) theory of gender performativity. These frameworks are employed not as fixed analytical categories but as interpretive lenses through which the instability, ambiguity, and performative dimensions of femininity can be examined.

In addition to textual analysis, the study draws on selected player discussions and supplementary lore materials as contextual sources. Publicly accessible discussions from Reddit ([r/dragonage](#)), *Dragon Age* Wiki and archived BioWare forum discussions were consulted to identify recurring interpretations surrounding Flemeth, Morrigan, motherhood, and moral ambiguity. Searches focused on character names and narrative concepts central to the study, including "Flemeth," "Morrigan," "Kieran," "Mythal," "mother," "The Mother," "Broodmother," "Dark Ritual," "family," "lineage," "inheritance," and "witch." Relevant discussions were selected on the basis of their thematic relevance to recurring issues of motherhood, femininity, bodily transformation, power, monstrosity, and moral ambiguity. Player comments and lore materials are not treated as representative empirical data, nor are they intended to reflect the views of the player community as a whole. Rather, they function as supplementary interpretive material that provides additional insight into how these characters and themes are discussed within fan communities. Their purpose is not to support generalizable claims about player reception, but to contextualize recurring patterns of interpretation surrounding the characters examined in this study.

The purpose of this methodological approach is not to produce generalizable findings but to offer a theoretically informed interpretation of how femininity, motherhood, and female power are constructed, destabilized, and renegotiated within a specific digital game narrative. Although *Dragon Age: The Veilguard* (2024) further expands the mythology surrounding Mythal and the Evanuris, it falls outside the scope of the present study. The analysis focuses on the narrative arc established between 2009 and 2014 because it encompasses the complete development of Flemeth and Morrigan as mother–daughter figures within the original *Dragon Age* narrative cycle. Including *The Veilguard* would require addressing a substantially different narrative context and set of character relationships that extend beyond the analytical focus of this study.

Case context: The *Dragon Age* series and the narrative position of Flemeth and Morrigan

The *Dragon Age* series, developed by BioWare and published between 2009 and 2014, constitutes one of the most influential fantasy role-playing franchises in contemporary digital game culture. Spanning multiple titles—*Dragon Age: Origins* (2009), *Dragon Age II* (2011), and *Dragon Age: Inquisition* (2014),

alongside expansion content—the series is distinguished by its emphasis on narrative choice, character development, and branching storylines that allow players to actively shape the game world.

Set in the fictional continent of Thedas, the series combines high fantasy conventions with complex political structures, religious conflict, and moral ambiguity. Unlike many mainstream role-playing games, *Dragon Age* foregrounds not only heroism and combat, but also questions of lineage, power, and historical continuity. In this narrative architecture, certain characters function not merely as participants in the story, but as forces that shape its underlying logic.

Within this framework, Flemeth and Morrigan provide a useful case through which to examine the intersection of the femme fatale and motherhood in digital games. Examining these two central witch figures across the *Dragon Age* series (BioWare, 2009–2014) highlights how femininity is negotiated through questions of lineage, power, and transformation. Rather than operating as secondary or decorative figures, Flemeth and Morrigan function as key drivers of narrative progression, genealogical continuity, and ontological disruption within the game world. Importantly, both characters exceed the category of the “strong female character,” a label that often masks underlying structural limitations in representation. Flemeth, as an archaic maternal figure, embodies a form of power that is simultaneously mythic, corporeal, and temporally expansive. Morrigan, by contrast, initially appears within the framework of the femme fatale, yet her narrative trajectory reveals a more complex negotiation between autonomy, inheritance, and transformation. Together, they form a relational dynamic through which femininity is not stabilized, but continuously reconfigured. In this sense, the figures of Flemeth and Morrigan can be understood as disrupting not only binary oppositions but also the broader narrative tendency to stabilize female identity within predetermined roles (Inceoğlu, 2015). To better understand how these representations evolve across the series, Table 1 outlines the shifting narrative functions of Flemeth and Morrigan within each major installment.

Game / Text	Narrative Position	Function of Flemeth	Function of Morrigan
<i>Dragon Age: Origins</i> (2009)	Main narrative / First encounter	Archaic mother; witch as potential threat; mechanism of bodily continuity and possession	Independent femme fatale; initiator of the Dark Ritual; carrier of lineage and future transformation
<i>Dragon Age: Origins – Awakening</i> (2010)	Expansion / Monstrous motherhood narrative	Absent, but thematically echoed through figures such as the Broodmother and The Mother	Absent
<i>Dragon Age: Origins – Witch Hunt</i> (2010)	DLC / Departure narrative	Reframed through Morrigan’s perspective as a force exceeding mortality	Daughter confronting the maternal figure; articulating autonomy and future trajectory
<i>Dragon Age II</i> (2011)	Main narrative / Epic continuity	Mythic entity guiding prophecy; rescuer figure intervening in lineage and fate	Absent in gameplay; persists as a narrative and genealogical presence
<i>Dragon Age: Inquisition</i> (2014)	Main narrative / High political context	Embodiment of Mythal; exceeds maternal protection; operates as a transhistorical force	Motherhood combined with political and magical authority; autonomous yet genealogically embedded

Table 1. Narrative positioning of Flemeth and Morrigan across the *Dragon Age* Series

As demonstrated in Table 1, both Flemeth and Morrigan occupy positions that extend beyond conventional character roles. Their functions are not limited to interpersonal relationships or episodic narrative arcs; instead, they operate at the level of continuity, inheritance, and transformation. Flemeth’s presence persists across time and bodies, suggesting a model of motherhood that is not bound to care, but to survival and transmission. Morrigan’s trajectory, meanwhile, reveals how femininity can shift from performative seduction to strategic maternal agency without resolving its internal contradictions.

This continuity across titles is significant because it demonstrates that motherhood and the femme fatale are not static archetypes within the series, but evolving configurations shaped by narrative context, player choice, and shifting power structures.

In this sense, *Dragon Age* does not merely include complex female characters; it reorganizes the narrative logic through which femininity operates. Flemeth and Morrigan are not positioned at the margins of the story, but at its core—where questions of power, lineage, and existence are negotiated.

Flemeth: Abjection, space, and trans-corporeal motherhood

Flemeth's representation in *Dragon Age: Origins* is structured through the collapse of spatial, bodily, and temporal boundaries. She inhabits the Korcari Wilds, a liminal space at the edge of the civilized world, where distinctions between culture and nature begin to dissolve. This positioning is not incidental; it reinforces her characterization as a figure that exists outside normative social and moral frameworks. Her narrative is framed through motifs of revenge, loss, and transformation, situating her within a lineage of mythic figures associated with destructive maternal power. Her title as the "Mother of Vengeance" evokes parallels with figures such as Clytemnestra, whose actions destabilize the boundaries between justice, violence, and maternal identity. As Paglia argues, such figures represent a form of female power that precedes and resists patriarchal order, aligning femininity with forces of chaos, rage, and continuity (Paglia, 2004, p. 115). Within this framework, Flemeth's relationship to her daughters cannot be understood through conventional maternal paradigms; instead, it operates through control, transmission, and the perpetuation of power.

Rather than embodying a nurturing maternal presence, Flemeth redefines motherhood as a mechanism of continuity. This association between motherhood and transformation is not limited to her character but recurs throughout the *Dragon Age* universe. The grotesque figure of the Broodmother, whose body functions as a site of forced reproduction and bodily corruption, reveals how maternity is repeatedly linked to excess, instability, and horror within the series. As described in Hespith's poem, the creation of a Broodmother is associated with violation, bodily transformation, and the collapse of human identity. This logic reaches its clearest expression in the "Flemeth's Real Grimoire" quest, where the possibility that Flemeth transfers her essence into her daughters reframes maternity as a site of existential ambiguity rather than biological continuity. As illustrated in Image 1, her visual design reinforces this liminal status, combining human features with elements that suggest transformation, excess, and instability.

Image 1. Flemeth's second appearance in *Dragon Age II* (BioWare, 2011). Screenshot captured from gameplay footage (YouTube upload by jj0ck33).

As Kristeva argues, "abjection is above all ambiguity... it does not radically cut off the subject from what threatens it" (1982, p.9). Flemeth exemplifies this condition. She is neither fully self nor other, neither protector nor antagonist. Instead, she occupies a position that resists stable categorization, producing a

sense of unease that is consistently reflected in player interpretations. Player discussions frequently describe Flemeth as “unknowable” or “beyond morality,” reinforcing the difficulty of reducing her to a fixed identity. This ambiguity is further intensified through her transformation into a High Dragon. The scale, materiality, and excess of this form exceed the classical notion of the bounded, complete body described by Bakhtin (1984). Rather than representing a loss of humanity, the transformation signals an expansion of corporeal possibility. In this sense, Flemeth aligns with Creed’s concept of the monstrous-feminine: not as a deviation from femininity, but as its amplification through reproduction, transformation, and archaic power. Importantly, Flemeth’s power is not visual but structural. She does not function as an object of the gaze, but as a force that shapes the conditions of the narrative itself. This distinguishes her from traditional representations of female characters within game and film, where power is often tied to visibility or desirability.

Image 2. Flemeth in her High Dragon form (Dragon Age: Origins, BioWare, 2009). Image sourced from Dragon Age Wiki (Fandom).

As illustrated in Image 2, Flemeth’s transformation into a High Dragon represents the collapse of the bounded human body, aligning with Bakhtin’s notion of the grotesque body and Creed’s concept of the monstrous-feminine.

Morrigan and the dark ritual: Maternal agency as narrative transformation

Morrigan’s trajectory introduces a different, yet equally complex configuration of femininity. While she initially appears within the framework of the femme fatale—marked by emotional distance, strategic communication, and sexual autonomy—her characterization shifts through narrative progression. Player interpretations frequently emphasize that her behavior is learned rather than inherent, reframing femininity as a form of maternal transmission. Raised in isolation, Morrigan approaches social interaction as strategy rather than affect. Narrative descriptions suggest that she performs the role of the “innocent girl” to lure and manipulate male subjects, using seduction not as an expression of desire but as a tool of control. In this sense, her femininity appears less as a stable identity than as a strategic and context-dependent performance.

This dynamic reaches its critical point in the Dark Ritual. The ritual transforms reproduction from a biological or symbolic function into a central narrative mechanism. Morrigan proposes the conception of a child that will absorb the soul of an Old God, thereby preventing the sacrificial death that would otherwise conclude the narrative. As illustrated in Image 3, Morrigan occupies a position of control within the ritual, reframing reproduction as a strategic narrative intervention rather than a passive or purely biological process. This ambiguity is also reflected in player discussions, which frequently resist stable categorizations of Morrigan as either “good” or “evil.” As one player remarks, “*She’s not evil... but she’s definitely not good either. She just does what she thinks is necessary.*” Another notes, “*You never really know if she cares or if she’s just using you.*” These interpretations reproduce rather than resolve the uncertainty surrounding Morrigan’s character, reinforcing her position as a figure that resists fixed moral and gendered classifications.

Image 3. Morrigan during the Dark Ritual sequence in *Dragon Age: Origins* (BioWare, 2009). Screenshot captured by the author from gameplay footage.

This moment fundamentally disrupts the binary between the nurturing mother and the dangerous seductress. The maternal body is no longer aligned with care or sacrifice, but with strategy, survival, and transformation. The implications of the Dark Ritual extend beyond narrative choice and into the ontological structure of the game world. As noted in *Dragon Age* lore, the ritual enables the soul of the *Old God Urthemiel* to be transferred into Morrigan's unborn child, thereby preventing its destruction upon death (*Dragon Age Wiki*, n.d.). In this configuration, the maternal body becomes a vessel not only of biological reproduction, but of metaphysical continuity. This transformation fundamentally alters the meaning of motherhood within the narrative. Morrigan does not give birth to a child in the conventional sense; she becomes the mediator of an ancient, pre-human force. The child, Kieran, is not simply offspring, but a site where divine, monstrous, and human elements converge. This convergence reinforces the instability of maternal identity, aligning it with what Kristeva defines as a space of ambiguity between self and other. Importantly, this dynamic also repositions Morrigan's agency. Rather than being subsumed into motherhood, she orchestrates it as a strategic act, controlling the transmission of power across generations. In this sense, the Dark Ritual exemplifies a form of maternal agency that exceeds both nurturing and destructive archetypes, situating motherhood within a broader framework of ontological transformation.

This complexity suggests that motherhood in *Dragon Age* cannot be reduced to a singular meaning. As Welldon (2019) argues, maternal identity encompasses not only care but also power, ambivalence, and forms of relational control. Morrigan's transition into motherhood does not neutralize her earlier traits; rather, it reconfigures them within a different set of narrative stakes.

When Morrigan reappears in *Dragon Age: Inquisition*, this transformation becomes even more apparent. As the mother of Kieran, she operates simultaneously within political, magical, and maternal domains. Her authority is not diminished by motherhood; it is expanded through it. Protection, in this case, is not expressed through self-sacrifice, but through strategy, knowledge, and autonomy.

Discussion: Reconfiguring femininity through maternal ambiguity

Importantly, the ambiguity of motherhood identified in Flemeth and Morrigan is not limited to these characters alone. The broader *Dragon Age* universe repeatedly associates maternity with transformation, excess, and monstrosity. Figures such as the Broodmother and The Mother present reproduction not as a nurturing condition but as a site of bodily violation, contamination, and uncontrolled generation. These representations resonate strongly with Kristeva's concept of abjection and Creed's formulation of the *monstrous-feminine*, where the maternal body simultaneously functions as a source of life and horror. Within this wider narrative context, Flemeth and Morrigan emerge not as isolated exceptions but as part of a recurring tension through which motherhood is continuously reimagined.

The analysis of Flemeth and Morrigan reveals that *Dragon Age* does not simply reproduce existing gender archetypes but actively reconfigures them through narrative structure. While these characters

initially appear to align with recognizable categories—the monstrous mother and the *femme fatale*—they ultimately destabilize these classifications by exceeding their boundaries. Flemeth represents a form of archaic maternal power that operates beyond the limits of the human body, transforming motherhood into a process of continuity, possession, and trans-corporeal existence. Morrigan, by contrast, redefines maternal identity through agency and strategic intervention, positioning reproduction as a deliberate and controlled act rather than a passive biological function.

Taken together, these characters demonstrate that femininity in digital games cannot be fully understood through binary oppositions such as nurturing/destructive or passive/active. Instead, *Dragon Age* presents femininity as a contingent and shifting configuration shaped by power, transformation, and contradiction. This instability resonates with Butler's (1990) understanding of gender as performative rather than essential. Rather than offering alternative representations of femininity, the series exposes the processes through which femininity is produced, negotiated, and contested.

This process is further complicated by the role of the player. As studies of interactive dramaturgy suggest, digital game characters are not fixed entities but dynamic constructs that emerge through the interaction of narrative systems and player agency (Zamandar Başoğlu, 2021). In this sense, femininity is not only performed within the narrative but also co-produced through gameplay. The significance of Flemeth and Morrigan therefore extends beyond characterization. Both figures operate at the level of narrative logic, shaping questions of continuity, identity, and power while remaining open to multiple interpretations. This dynamic reflects broader shifts in digital game narratives, where meaning emerges through ongoing processes of interpretation and circulation across platforms and player communities (Zamandar Başoğlu, in press).

Digital games thus offer a unique space in which traditional gender categories can be destabilized rather than simply reproduced. As Murray (1997) argues, digital environments function as spaces of narrative possibility, while Aarseth (1997) emphasizes that meaning emerges through interaction rather than fixed textual structures. From this perspective, femininity in games is not merely represented but actively negotiated through player engagement. Characters such as Flemeth and Morrigan therefore reveal not only alternative representations of women, but also alternative ways of imagining femininity itself.

Conclusion

This study set out to examine how the intersection of the *femme fatale* archetype and motherhood is articulated in digital games through the case of *Dragon Age*. Although the series is not a recent production, its narrative configurations reveal tensions that remain highly relevant to contemporary discussions on gender representation.

In recent years, the hypersexualized female figure has increasingly been replaced by the "strong female character," often defined through autonomy, resilience, and combat competence. However, this shift does not necessarily indicate a fundamental transformation in the representation of femininity. Rather, it introduces a different form of regulation, in which acceptable femininity is redefined through strength while remaining controlled, legible, and ultimately contained. From a communication design perspective, this suggests that character design, visual symbolism, and interactive narrative structures do not merely communicate gendered meanings but actively participate in their production and negotiation.

What remains comparatively underrepresented is the possibility of feminine subjectivities that are unstable, contradictory, or unsettling. The analysis of Flemeth and Morrigan demonstrates that *Dragon Age* offers a configuration in which femininity is not resolved into coherent or idealized forms. Instead, these characters inhabit positions that are simultaneously maternal, dangerous, strategic, and excessive. Flemeth exemplifies a form of maternal power that cannot be reconciled with nurturing or moral stability, while Morrigan redefines motherhood as a site of agency, calculation, and transformation. Together, they complicate conventional expectations surrounding female characters and the forms of femininity they are expected to embody. From this perspective, the issue is not simply the absence of strong female

characters, but the limited range of femininities that are considered representable. While strength has become an acceptable attribute, abjection, monstrosity, and moral ambiguity remain marginal. Yet these dimensions open space for more complex and less regulated forms of representation.

Ultimately, this study suggests that expanding the representation of women in digital games requires moving beyond both sexualization and idealized strength, toward figures that can embody contradiction, excess, and discomfort. In this sense, the value of Flemeth and Morrigan lies not in their exceptionality, but in the alternative possibilities they make visible—possibilities that remain comparatively underdeveloped within the broader landscape of digital game narratives.

Statement

Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Beyanı | Research and Publication Ethics Statement

This study has been prepared in accordance with the rules of scientific research and publication ethics.

Etik Kurul İzni | Ethics Committee Approval

No approval from the Ethics Committee is required for this study.

Üretken Yapay Zekâ Araçları Kullanım Beyanı | Declaration of Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence Tools

Generative AI tools were used for language editing and structural assistance.

Çıkar Çatışması Beyanı | Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The author(s) of this study have no conflicts of interest.

Finansal Destek Beyanı | Financial Support Statement

This study has not received funding from any institution, organisation or project.

References

- Aarseth, E. (1997). *Cybertext: Perspectives on ergodic literature*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Bakhtin, M. (1984). *Rabelais and his world* (H. Iswolsky, Trans.). Indiana University Press.
- BioWare. (2009). *Dragon Age: Origins* [Video game]. Electronic Arts.
- BioWare. (2010). *Dragon Age: Origins – Awakening* [Expansion pack]. Electronic Arts.
- BioWare. (2010). *Dragon Age: Origins – Witch Hunt* [Downloadable content]. Electronic Arts.
- BioWare. (2011). *Dragon Age II* [Video game]. Electronic Arts.
- BioWare. (2014). *Dragon Age: Inquisition* [Video game]. Electronic Arts.
- Bogost, I. (2007). *Persuasive games: The expressive power of videogames*. MIT Press.
- Butler, J. (1990). *Gender trouble: Feminism and the subversion of identity*. Routledge.
- Consalvo, M. (2008). Crunched by passion: Women game developers and workplace challenges. *Proceedings of the 2008 Digital Games Research Association Conference*.
- Creed, B. (1993). *The monstrous-feminine: Film, feminism, psychoanalysis*. Routledge.
- Doane, M.A. (1991). *Femmes Fatales* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315021171>
- Downs, E., & Smith, S. L. (2010). Keeping abreast of hypersexuality: A video game character content analysis. *Sex Roles*, 62(11–12), 721–733. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-009-9637-1>
- Dragon Age Wiki. (n.d.). Flemeth. *Fandom*. Retrieved April 2026, from <https://dragonage.fandom.com/wiki/Flemeth>
- Glick, P., & Fiske, S. T. (2001). An ambivalent alliance: Hostile and benevolent sexism as complementary justifications for gender inequality. *American Psychologist*, 56(2), 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.56.2.109>
- Guerrilla Games. (2017). *Horizon Zero Dawn* [Video game]. Sony Interactive Entertainment.
- Gürses Akbaykal, İ. (2013). *Transgresyon ve anarşi: Fotoğrafta aşırılığın estetiği* [Doctoral dissertation, Ege University].
- Herbst, K. C. (2004). Lara's lethal and loaded mission: Transposing reproduction and destruction. In S. A. Inness (Ed.), *Action chicks: New images of tough women in popular culture* (pp. 21–45). Palgrave Macmillan.
- İnceoğlu, İ. (2015). Beyaz perdede kadın anlatısı: Mavi Dalga filminin feminist incelemesi. *Fe Dergi: Feminist Eleştiri*, 7(2), 87–94. https://doi.org/10.1501/Fe0001_0000000145
- jjöck33. (2011, March 12). *Dragon Age 2 – Flemeth's second appearance* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AUi8OoymHFk>
- Kennedy, H. W. (2002). Lara Croft: Feminist icon or cyberbimbo? *Game Studies*, 2(2). <http://www.gamestudies.org/0202/kennedy>
- Kristeva, J. (1982). *Powers of horror: An essay on abjection* (L. S. Roudiez, Trans.). Columbia University Press.
- Martins, N., Williams, D. C., Ratan, R. A., & Harrison, K. (2009). The virtual musculature: Body ideals in video games. *Mass Communication and Society*, 12(1), 96–113.

- Mulvey, L. (1975). Visual pleasure and narrative cinema. *Screen*, 16(3), 6–18. <https://doi.org/10.1093/screen/16.3.6>
- Murray, J. (1997). *Hamlet on the holodeck*. MIT Press.
- Naughty Dog. (2020). *The Last of Us Part II* [Video game]. Sony Interactive Entertainment.
- Paglia, C. (1990). *Sexual personae: Art and decadence from Nefertiti to Emily Dickinson*. Yale University Press.
- Remedy Entertainment. (2019). *Control* [Video game]. 505 Games.
- Rockstar Games. (2013). *Grand Theft Auto V* [Video game]. Rockstar Games.
- Ruberg, B. (2019). *Video games have always been queer*. New York University Press.
- Shaw, A. (2014). *Gaming at the edge: Sexuality and gender at the margins of gamer culture*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Sicart, M. (2013). *Beyond choices: The design of ethical gameplay*. MIT Press.
- Tompkins, J. E., Lynch, T., Van Driel, I. I., & Fritz, N. (2020). Kawaii killers and femme fatales: A textual analysis of female characters signifying benevolent and hostile sexism in video games. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 64(2), 236–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08838151.2020.1718960>
- Welldon, E. V. (2019). *Mother, Madonna, whore: The idealization and denigration of motherhood* (1st ed.). Routledge.
- Zamandar Başoğlu, A. B. (2021). *Sinema anlatı yapısındaki karakter olgusunun dijital oyunlara yansımaları: İnteraktif dramaturji ve kahramanlık* [Master's thesis, Ege University].
- Zamandar Başoğlu, A. B. (in press). Who tells the story? The Fiction² model and the algorithmic reconstruction of narrative. In F. Savaş Gün, N. Balkır, A. N. Akören, & D. B. İz (Eds.), *Visual practices in art and design (Vol. II)*. Peter Lang.